

Cloud platforms Lead to Open and Universal access for people with Disabilities and for All

D403.1. Consolidated evaluation report

Project Acronym **Cloud4all**
Grant Agreement Number **FP7-289016**

Deliverable No. **D403.1**
Work package No. **WP403**
Work package Title **Iterative pilots**
Authors **TECH, CERTH, UPM, SDC, HDM**
Status **Draft**
Dissemination Level **Public**
Delivery Date **31/10/2015**
Number of Pages **51**

Keyword List

Evaluation, user experience, UX, pilot, iteration, UCD, user research, usability, acceptance.

Version History

Table 1. Version history

Revision	Date	Author	Organization	Description
1	29/10/2015	Nacho Madrid, Iván Carmona, Eleni Chalkia	TECH, CERTH	First draft
2	30/10/2015	Christophe Strobbe	HdM	Review on MM evaluation
3	31/10/2015	Nacho Madrid, Ivan Carmona	TECH	Version for PR
4	04/11/2015	Manuel Ortega	TECH	Comments from PC
5	01/12/2015	ELAC	ELAC	Ethical review
4	17/12/2015	Nacho Madrid	TECH	Final version

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction.....	2
1.1 Objectives of this document	2
1.2 Innovation beyond the state of the art.....	2
1.3 Relationship with other WPs and Activities	2
1.4 Structure of the document.....	4
2 Pilot evaluation framework, experimental plans and logistics.....	5
2.1 Cloud4all evaluation with end users	5
2.1.1 Cloud4all evaluation objectives.....	5
2.1.2 Cloud4all evaluation scenarios	6
2.2 Cloud4all evaluation with developers.....	7
2.3 Cloud4all evaluation with stakeholders.....	8
3 Evaluation of Cloud4all tools, solutions and systems.....	10
3.1 Usability and accessibility of the PMT/PCP tools.....	10
3.1.1 Introduction	10
3.1.2 Functional tools	11
3.1.3 Non-functional tools.....	12
3.1.4 Proofs of concept.....	14
3.2 Usability and accessibility of the SAT	15
3.2.1 Introduction	15
3.2.2 Semantic alignment tool (SAT) (1 st iteration).....	15
3.2.3 Semantics alignment tool (SAT) (2 nd iteration).....	15
3.3 Evaluation of the MM performance.....	16
4 Cloud4all from the perspective of beneficiaries.....	23
4.1 User research with end-users	23
4.1.1 End-user involvement in Cloud4all.....	23
4.1.2 On users' needs and preferences with technology.....	23
4.1.3 On end-users' concept acceptance	29
4.2 User research with developers	31
4.2.1 Developers' involvement in Cloud4all.....	31

4.2.2	Insights about the integration process and Cloud4all acceptance	31
4.3	User research with stakeholders.....	33
4.3.1	Stakeholders' involvement in Cloud4all	33
4.3.2	Cloud4all from the perspective of stakeholders	33
5	Future research topics in Cloud4all.....	35
5.1	Research priorities from project partners.....	35
5.1.1	High priority research topics	35
5.1.2	Medium priority research topics	36
5.2	Insights from user and expert forums.....	40
6	Conclusions.....	42
7	References.....	45
List of Tables		
Table 1.	Version history	ii
Table 2.	List of abbreviations.....	vii
Table 3.	Summary of matchmaker accuracies.....	20
List of Figures		
Figure 1.	Overview of the Cloud4all evaluation framework	3
Figure 2.	Cloud4all 1 st evaluation phase. Auto-configuration scenario	6
Figure 3.	Cloud4all 2 nd evaluation phase. Auto-configuration scenario	7
Figure 4.	Interpretation of the UX score scale used for quantitative evaluation	10
Figure 5.	Evolution of the ease of use of the PMT in different versions.....	11
Figure 6.	Three screenshots of the PMT with extended functions prototype.....	12
Figure 7.	Example paper mock-ups for the PCP advanced prototype	13
Figure 8.	Several wireframe instances for the <i>Auto-adaptation</i> scenario	13
Figure 9.	Two wireframe instances for the <i>Context-specific recommendations</i> scenario	14
Figure 10.	Evolution of the ease of use of the SAT in different versions	16
Figure 11.	Two examples of user research activities at pilot sites.....	23
Figure 12.	Configuration in Platform A (Windows) without Cloud4All	26
Figure 13.	Configuration in Windows with Cloud4all (PMT).....	27

Figure 14. Comparison of <i>Perceived usability</i> and <i>Autonomy/Competence</i> feelings with and without using PMT.....	27
Figure 15. Comparison of performance and user experience metrics in Windows with/without Cloud4all.....	28
Figure 16. Comparison of performance and user experience metrics in Linux, Android and Java with/without Cloud4all.....	29
Figure 17. End-users assessment of the Ease of use of the Cloud4all concept over the three project evaluation phases	29
Figure 18. End-users assessment of the Usefulness of the Cloud4all concept over the three project evaluation phases	30
Figure 19. End-users assessment of the Intention to use of the Cloud4all concept over the three project evaluation phases.....	30
Figure 20. Pictures from the user and expert forums organized over the project	40

List of abbreviations

Table 2. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AT	Assistive Technology
ATM	Automated Teller Machine
DTV	Digital Television
EASTIN	European Assistive Technology Information Network
GPII	Global Public Infrastructure Initiative
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MM	Matchmaker
N&P	Needs and preferences
OS	Operating System
PCP	Personal Control Panel
PMT	Preferences Management Tool
RBMM	Rule-based Matchmaker
SAT	Semantic Alignment Tool
SMS	Short Message Service
STMM	Statistical Matchmaker
TTS	Text-to-speech
UCD	User-centred design
UI	User interface
USB	Universal Serial Bus
UX	User eXperience

Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a consolidated report of the three evaluation phases conducted in Cloud4all. The evaluation in Cloud4all studies the user experience and acceptance of the prototypes created, and provides iterative feedback to the design and development teams for the improvement of the different systems and applications. Moreover, the research conducted should also provide useful recommendations for the exploitation teams.

Firstly, the document shows the results of the **evaluation of usability and accessibility** for the different tools, solutions and systems produced in Project. One of the main tools evaluated is the Preference Management Tool (PMT) / Personal Control Panel (PCP) that collects and stores users' needs and preferences (N&P) and allows them to edit their preferred settings. The resulting UX metrics have been positive over the Project, especially with the last version assessed that could be qualified as 'Excellent' according to the UX scale used. More moderate have been the evaluation of the SAT tool for developer, although its usability have been also improved over the Project. The evaluation of other non-functional prototypes and proof of concepts have also been successful providing inputs for the design and development teams. The **performance of the different types of matchmakers** was also investigated over the three evaluation phases, showing that apparently the rule-based matchmaker outperforms the statistical matchmaker.

Secondly, **user research with end-users, developers and stakeholders** have provided additional knowledge on the current difficulties, their N&Ps and the way in which Cloud4all could better address them. For **end-users**, it has been shown that the most appropriate settings depend on several factors, being a complex task that not all users are able to perform with autonomy and competence. Cloud4all tools benefit users by making the process of specifying the preferred settings easier, and auto-configuration allows users to perform common tasks better and easier in both familiar and non-familiar systems. For **developers**, Cloud4all research showed that they were very positive in their considerations and the potential of the Project, but they also pointed out several issues related to the integration process (such as the lack of complete documentation or the low maturity of the architecture at the time the integration took place). These are difficulties that are inherent to a research project in which several components are developed and updated constantly, but seem to be easily addressed at later stages when a stable version of the architecture is in place. For **stakeholders**, Cloud4all is also quite usable and useful, confirming the opinions of the end-users, although they also stressed that some users may need improvements in the PMT (such as including settings for sign language and providing additional guidance for those with cognitive impairments or low digital literacy).

Finally, this deliverable ends with some **recommendations for further research** beyond the Cloud4all project that have arisen from the consortium members and from end-users and experts participating in forums.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this document

This document is the outcome of various activities included in *WP403: Iterative pilots*, especially of *A403.3 Pilot results consolidation and impact assessment*. This activity aims at fulfilling the following operational objectives:

- OO.8.11: To study all factors affecting the user experience with, and acceptance of the prototypes, including, perceived usefulness, ease of access and interaction, and satisfaction, and provide an integrated feedback for the enhancement of the posterior versions.
- OO.8.12: To provide iterative feedback for the development of each project prototype, with emphasis to the effect timing of the 3 types of matching algorithms.
- OO.8.13: To review and consolidate the outcome and experience gained from all the evaluations and, thereby provide input to project development and exploitation teams as well as to the society, through guidelines and standardization recommendations.

This document summarized the procedures followed in the project, in order to ensure that the UCD approach is adopted and applied in the design and development of interfaces and applications.

1.2 Innovation beyond the state of the art

The aim of WP403 was not to bring innovation, but to enable the design iteration cycles of the project applications, thus supporting the iterative UCD approach adopted in Cloud4all. However, user research with Cloud4all has improved our knowledge on the needs and preferences of end-users and the best ways of addressing them.

1.3 Relationship with other WPs and Activities

This document, as part of the Cloud4all evaluation framework, is related to a great number of deliverables, work packages and activities. Figure 1 shows a summary of the relationships between different activities involved in the Cloud4all evaluation framework.

Figure 1. Overview of the Cloud4all evaluation framework

Firstly, this document is mainly related to several deliverables from WP401 that defined the methodologies and results of the UCD approach adopted in the project:

- *D401.1. Cloud4All user population and UCD Implementation Plan* (Sainz de Salces, Melcher, Ochoa & Cheetam, 2012). This document defines the different user groups involved in Cloud4all and the procedures for their recruitment and involvement. Moreover, it stated the UCD approach to be adopted in the project and describe a number of methodologies to be used.
- *D401.2. UI Style-guide and controlling mechanisms* (Melcher, Pawlowski & Leuteritz, 2012). This style guide provides general advice for the creation of User Interfaces, both applicable to individually programmed solutions and to automatic adaptations. Moreover, it defined controlling mechanisms to ensure that the UCD approach is adopted in the project.
- *D401.3. UCD and UI Style-guide usage in the project* (Madrid, Carmona, de Lera, & Ortega-Moral, 2015). The document summarized the effective implementation of the UCD approach in Cloud4all. It described the results on user involvement, as well as the procedures followed during design and development of user interfaces.

Secondly, the deliverable present results from the pilot evaluations, the implementation of which was planned in WP402 deliverables:

- *D402.1 Pilot scenarios* (Chalkia & Prentza, 2013). The document described and identified the scenarios to be tested over the different evaluation phases in Cloud4all.
- *D402.2.1-3. Pilots evaluation framework, experimental plans and tools* (Chalkia et al. 2014; Madrid et al. 2015; Sainz et al. 2013). This set of deliverables detail the specific evaluation framework for each of the evaluation phases.

Finally, this deliverable summarizes and consolidates the results from each of the evaluation phases that have been documented in internal deliverables ID403.1, ID403.2 and ID403.3 (Chalkia, Pujol, Carmona, Peter & Madrid, 2013; Madrid, Chalkia, Wolbers, Gruber, Carmona & de los Rios, 2014; Madrid, Chalkia, Gruber, Carmona, de los Rios & Strobbe, 2015).

1.4 Structure of the document

First, Section 2 describes the pilot evaluation framework, experimental plans and logistics adopted for each of the three evaluation phases in the project. Section 3 focuses on the results, in terms of usability, accessibility and user experience, obtained during the evaluation of the Cloud4all tools, solutions and systems. Next, Section 4 describes the results of user research activities with end-users, developers, and stakeholders that have provided an overview on user needs and preferences and the better way in which Cloud4all can address them. In Section 5, some future research topics in Cloud4all are identified both from the perspective of the consortium members and from the point of view of end-users and experts. Finally, Section 6 presents the main conclusions of the document.

2 Pilot evaluation framework, experimental plans and logistics

2.1 Cloud4all evaluation with end users

2.1.1 Cloud4all evaluation objectives

Each of the three evaluation phases of Cloud4all had different objectives based on the maturity of the tools and the information the developers needed to extract from the users to evolve their developments. Below, the objectives of each evaluation phase are presented. Going through the following objectives of each iteration phase, the evolvement of Cloud4all evaluation tests is evident.

- **1st evaluation phase of Cloud4all:**
 - Introduce the concept of Cloud4all to users and getting their general reaction and early input.
 - Present the ability of the basic infrastructure to automatically launch and set up access solutions for users according to their preferences.
 - Realize very early preliminary testing of *matchmaker* technologies for products that the user has not specified any preferences yet, in *Windows* and in *Linux* environment.
 - Compare the results of the *rule-based matchmaker* with the results of the *statistical matchmaker*. The matchmakers are the features that provide the intelligence of the Cloud4all system, by matching with each other all the different components that participate in the procedure.
 - Compare the results of the *rule-based matchmaker* and the *results of the statistic matchmaker* with experts.
- **2nd evaluation phase of Cloud4all:**
 - Identify how Cloud4all will foster digital inclusion by improving user experience, in comparison to the current way of performing a common task in different, familiar or not, non-personalized solutions.
- **3rd evaluation phase of Cloud4all:**
 - Evaluate the user experience with the Cloud4all auto-configuration procedure.
 - Evaluate the improved use of different devices and solutions.

- Evaluate the acceptance of the context-related changes functionality.
- Evaluate the management of Needs and Preferences with the PMT.

2.1.2 Cloud4all evaluation scenarios

Cloud4all pilot scenarios started to be prepared by the very beginning of the project, based on Use Cases described in D101.2 (Gemou, 2012). The first deliverable in which the pilot scenarios were introduced was D402.1 (Chalkia & Prentza, 2013), which was submitted in the second year of the project, drafting the pilot scenarios for all 3 iteration phases. The detailed pilot scenarios though were updated in each iteration phase, and they have been reported in each respective pilot framework deliverable, namely D402.2.1 for the 1st iteration phase, D402.2.2 for the 2nd iteration phase and D402.2.3 for the 3rd iteration phase (Chalkia et al. 2014; Madrid et al. 2015; Sainz et al. 2013).

As the objectives of each evaluation phase have evolved, the scenarios for the user tests have evolved too. Thus in the **1st evaluation phase** a guided scenario was realized by the users in which they had to set their preferences using a simplified tool. The preferences were captured in the form of application specific settings, which means that the facilitator noted the value that each specific setting of the specific application under evaluation had, after explaining it to the user and defining the effect of this setting to the entire solution interface. The scenario was that the user would identify his/her preferences first in *Windows* and then go to *Linux* and evaluate how the settings were inferred in that OS. Then the user would have to do the procedure vice-versa, i.e. identify the preferences in *Linux* and then go to *Windows* and evaluate how the settings were inferred in that OS. Thus we had two different sets of settings to compare. One set of settings the user defined in *Windows* (Token A) and compare them with the inferred settings from *Linux* to *Windows* (Log A). And a second set of settings the user defined in *Linux* (Token B) and compare them with the inferred settings from *Windows* to *Linux* (Log B). The aforementioned procedure is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Cloud4all 1st evaluation phase. Auto-configuration scenario

Moving forward to the **2nd evaluation phase**, the developments evolved and so did the procedure. The users no longer used application-specific settings to define their N&Ps, but used the Cloud4all *Preferences Management Tool (PMT)*, which uses common terms. Common terms are terms that harmonize the application-specific settings and values throughout all the applications used in Cloud4all. Then, the users had a more user-friendly tool in order to define and explore their N&Ps which were now captured in the needs and preferences server and retrieved from there. Additionally the users in the 2nd evaluation

phase had the possibility to navigate between different devices and not only in *Windows* and *Linux*. Thus, *Android OS*, *Java* mobile phones and other Cloud4all applications were made available to them. The procedure, which is depicted in Figure 3, asks the user to use the PMT in Platform A to define their N&Ps and create a token and use this token to login to Platform B and evaluate the inferred settings.

Figure 3. Cloud4all 2nd evaluation phase. Auto-configuration scenario

Finally, at the 3rd evaluation phase, which is the last evaluation phase, more naturalistic scenarios have been evaluated. A set of devices and applications and also a token which will be set by the pilot facilitator based on their N&P, has been given to the users. The users were asked to navigate to these different devices and applications as if they were in their own environment and validate the auto-configuration procedure and results. The applications used were SP3 solutions that are close to the ones the users could find in their everyday life: Digital TV, Windows and Linux OS for laptop or desktop PCs, Java or Android phones, online banking app, and different AT solutions (such as NVDA, ORCA, Mobile accessibility, Read&Write Gold, and Cloud4Chrome).

2.2 Cloud4all evaluation with developers

Cloud4all provides various channels that can be used by developers in order to work with Cloud4all and GPII. A key solution for developers provided by the Cloud4all project, which was ready from very early stages of the project, is the **Semantic Alignment Tool (SAT)**, a

software module for the syntactic and semantic analysis of solutions, by taking into account the different adaptation dimensions of the offered Cloud4all applications, services and tools.

An early prototype of the SAT was tested during the **1st iteration**, showing that its usability was below the project expectations and that additional efforts should be allocated for its improvement. Therefore, one of the objectives of evaluation during the **2nd evaluation phase** was to test that the usability of the solution were effectively improved, fostering the acceptance of the Cloud4all concept and GPII framework by developers.

The results of the 2nd evaluation phase appeared to be more positive for the SAT, thus in the **3rd evaluation phase** the objective of the evaluation adopted a higher point of view, assessing all the material that was created for developers within Cloud4all including the developers' kit which encompasses the following:

- Guidelines about the installation of Cloud4all
- Guidelines about testing the Cloud4all/GPII architecture
- Guidelines about the integration of a new solution to Cloud4all/GPII
 - When the solution runs on a specific platform.
 - When the solution is web-based.
- Additional information like
 - GPII source code
 - Blog for the developers
 - Cloud4all wiki
 - Cloud4all/GPII issue tracker

2.3 Cloud4all evaluation with stakeholders

Since the stakeholders group in Cloud4all is such a broad one, the need of the identification of the needs of each subgroup was revealed early in the project. In each step of the evaluation different subgroups have been participating providing different feedback, but in a lot of cases the results were comparable.

At the **1st evaluation phase** only end-users organizations participated. Participants with different profiles of disability were involved in the evaluation; however, as the end-users provided a personal view of their N&Ps, it was important to involve also expert representatives from end-users organizations in order to gather as well a wider overview and experience over the N&Ps of the different user groups. To that end, expert representatives from organizations of elderly people, visual impaired people, people with

learning difficulties and cognitive impairments, low literacy and people with dyslexia formed the panel of stakeholders in the 1st evaluation phase of Cloud4all.

As the project evolved in the **2nd evaluation phase**, stakeholders with different profiles (governments, service providers, caregivers, end users' experts) were involved in qualitative data gathering, to complement the end users' and developers' evaluations. The goal of the stakeholders' participation was to gather their impressions and qualitative feedback on the concepts, tools and the whole Cloud4all process from a different perspective. Therefore, the evaluation with the different stakeholders was exploratory and not guided by a specific research question. This was achieved mainly by their participation in structured focus groups organized around concrete research topics like the Cloud4all/GPII concept and auto-configuration scenario, the context-related changes scenario, the optimum N&P gathering scenario, the GPII marketplace and recommendation system scenario, etc.

Finally, during the **3rd evaluation phase** a more focused feedback was needed from the stakeholders. For this reason, stakeholders participating in this evaluation sessions were selected among experts related with end user organizations as well as AT providers and caregivers. Stakeholders with a more industrial vision, such as ICT vendors and software industry representatives, policy makers, etc. were involved in Cloud4all through the Open Days planed and realized later on in the project, where Cloud4all were demonstrated and existing applications and tools have been experienced.

Thus, the goal of the stakeholders' evaluation in the 3rd evaluation iteration was to gather their impressions and qualitative feedback on the concepts, tools and the whole Cloud4all process (including installation) from two different perspectives:

- Which is the usefulness for users? (from stakeholders' point of view), and
- Which is the usefulness for stakeholders? (being the stakeholders as mediators/supporters of end-users organizations or AT providers).

Stakeholders were involved in structured focus groups where the whole Cloud4all concept (from installation to use on different devices) was presented. Based on this, stakeholders participated on discussions around the concrete research topics.

3 Evaluation of Cloud4all tools, solutions and systems

3.1 Usability and accessibility of the PMT/PCP tools

3.1.1 Introduction

Different versions of the PMT and the PCP have been tested by end-users over the three UCD iterations in the project. Some of these versions were fully functional at the time they were evaluated while others were just mock-ups, clickable prototypes or even initial design concepts addressing very specific functionalities. Therefore, the various PMT/PCP solutions tested could be categorised in three groups:

- 1. Functional tools:** These are the tools that are fully functional and can be used freely, allowing autonomous interaction by the user in a proper pilot scenario.
- 2. Non-functional tools:** These are low and medium fidelity prototypes that are not functional yet, but they are in a conceptual level. In order to be tested, we created either clickable or paper prototypes to foster discussion between test facilitators and end-users.
- 3. Proofs of concept:** These are either use cases or design concepts that were used to explore future functionalities of Cloud4all. Therefore, there is not a physical prototype with which the users could interact. Test facilitators used *PowerPoint* presentations or storytelling techniques to foster the dialogue with users.

Techniques used during evaluation cover user testing, interviews, questionnaires and focus groups. When evaluating the usability of a certain tool, different UX metrics have been collected such as perceived usability, usefulness, autonomy and competence, user success rates, and number of errors. These metrics are largely based in state of the art methods, techniques, and tools commonly used in the evaluation of UX (Hassenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006; Petrie & Bevan, 2009; Tullis & Albert, 2008). In order to allow for a comprehensive benchmarking of different metrics over different tools, the scores were calculated in a 100 points-scale than can be interpreted qualitatively: the quality of a tool can be considered 'OK' when the score is above 50, 'Good' if it is above 70, 'Excellent' if it is above 80, and 'Best' if it is above 90 points (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Interpretation of the UX score scale used for quantitative evaluation (Madrid et al., 2014)

In the next section, just the most relevant results for these metrics will be shown, but full quantitative and qualitative results from testing are reported in ID403.1, ID403.2 and ID403.3. (Chalkia et al., 2013; Madrid et al., 2014; Madrid et al., 2015).

3.1.2 Functional tools

3.1.2.1 PMT v1 with basic functions (1st iteration)

Participants liked the capacity of the PMT with basic functions to preview the changes the user makes at the preferences set and also the step-by-step-approach. However, users voiced their criticism concerning the usability in general and some single aspects. Participants got especially confused with some wording and the comprehension of icons.

3.1.2.2 PMT v1 with extended functions (1st iteration)

Participants were slightly more positive in their assessment about this version of the PMT compared with the PMT with basic functions, as measured by usability, usefulness and satisfaction metrics. However, the tasks to be performed were more complex and more explanations were necessary. As a result of the evaluations, several suggestions for improvement of the interface, both in terms of usability and accessibility, were communicated to designers to be taken into account for the next version of the PMT.

3.1.2.3 PMT v2 (2nd iteration)

In general, participants liked the idea and approach of the PMT, they thought that it was generally easy to use and with a quite well organised interface. The UX metrics collected also confirmed a better user experience of this version when compared with previous ones. On the other hand, users thought that some elements may be confusing and would need more description, and thus, not all parts of the graphical user interface were found fully usable. Especially blind users found difficulties while using the PMT with a screen reader, since it was not fully accessible at the time of the tests.

The evolution of UX metrics for the PMT v2 in comparison with the previous versions are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Evolution of the ease of use of the PMT in different versions

3.1.2.4 PMT v3 (3rd iteration)

The usability of the PMT was not directly assessed through user testing in the 3rd evaluation phase, and therefore UX metrics were not collected. However, it was demoed as part of the evaluation scenario and users discussed about it in focus groups. The PMT was considered easy to use by most of the users, and they suggested some improvements to cope with the needs and preferences of people with specific needs (e.g. users with motor impairments may need interaction alternatives and deaf users will benefit from sign language videos).

3.1.3 Non-functional tools

3.1.3.1 PMT with extended functions and sharing among peers (2nd iteration)

This PMT prototype included information that allowed the user to define different settings for different contexts. Also, different authentication methods were available, as well as the functionality that could allow users to share their settings with their peers. The tests were done using a clickable prototype (Figure 6) and asking users to think-aloud while performing a number of tasks (such as *Change the username*, *Create a USB key*, *Adjust the configuration helper*, and *Share preferences with a friend*).

Figure 6. Three screenshots of the PMT with extended functions prototype

Participants liked the idea of controlling their computer settings and be able to share them with other people. Most of them were successful in performing the tasks, although some needed some help. Certain usability issues were also found and communicated to the design team. Summarizing these issues, the prototype includes some technical terms and concepts that are rather complex for novice users and the information architecture of the application could be improved to provide them with navigation guidance.

3.1.3.2 PCP advanced prototype (2nd iteration)

The PCP advanced prototype was tested using a paper mock-up. It allowed the participants to familiarize with the tool and give their opinion about the contextual design and its functionalities. The prototype showed keyboard shortcuts to open the key control configuration or the side panel configuration, including sliders, +/- input field, on/off toggle and the radio buttons to adjust the preferences (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Example paper mock-ups for the PCP advanced prototype

The paper mock-ups were used as a support to discuss with users about the general design concept of the PCP. Most users understood the functionalities to be offered, but found concrete difficulties with some interaction patterns or design elements (e.g. some users found difficult to activate the interface by pressing keys at a time). They also provided some ideas for the improvement of the interface that were communicated to the design team.

3.1.3.3 PCP-MM feedback mechanisms (3rd iteration)

Two scenarios were discussed through wireframes: *Auto-adaptation* and *Context-specific recommendations*. Both mainly addressed options related with visual preferences and screen reader settings, but the concept could be applied to other setting categories.

In the *Auto-adaptation* scenario (Figure 8), the users' preferences are not available in the system (NVDA or yellow/black contrast theme), so a message is shown in the interface and then the options that have been auto-adapted are communicated.

Figure 8. Several wireframe instances for the *Auto-adaptation* scenario

The users gave some advice to fine-up the wording and suggested that the PMT/PCP should allow establishing specific settings if the AT launched is unfamiliar. For example, if the screen reader that is being launched is unfamiliar, the speech rate should be much lower than in the familiar screen reader).

In the *Context-specific recommendations* scenario (Figure 9), the interface should communicate that the environmental conditions have changed, so a new configuration is applied to adapt to this new context. Wireframes are discussed with users, who gave their opinion on wording and appeal. There were different opinions about if the system should apply changes automatically or should ask the user before any change:

- It was suggested that the recommended setting is applied automatically but keeping the option to cancel and back to the previous configuration if it is not suitable.
- Other users preferred to test it before, and if it is suitable, apply the change. To this last option, the users expected a button like “apply” / “save” or similar.

Figure 9. Two wireframe instances for the *Context-specific recommendations* scenario

3.1.4 Proofs of concept

3.1.4.1 Proposal of a new solution (2nd iteration)

The proposal of a new solution is part of the vision of the generic Cloud4all scenario. The idea is to define a mechanism to propose the optimal AT to the users according to their N&P set. There are two different situations: a) if more than one AT is installed on the device(s) that is/are used, and b) if there is no AT installed.

The concept and its potential benefits were well understood by the users. However, some users were confused when an unfamiliar AT was automatically launched and would like to receive more information about what settings are not available and what are the

alternatives. The results were used to improve the communication between Cloud4all components and the users. One example is the PCP-MM feedback mechanisms that were tested in the 3rd iteration.

3.1.4.2 Conflict resolution use case (3rd iteration)

Participants discussed a case in which two different persons using the same computer had different preferences for font size that do conflict. Cloud4all could offer two different solutions in this situation:

1. Automatically calculating the average font size from the two persons' preferences, and then auto-configuring the calculated font-size on the device.
2. Providing a notification to inform the users that the font size could not be auto-configured according to both preferences. Then an adjuster in the PCP would be activated to allow them to select a font-size that is adequate for both to work cooperatively on the device.

This case conflict resolution process seemed very interesting for some of the users. The users believe that the first solution (averaging the settings) would not cover the needs of nobody. They suggested other options, such as splitting the screen in two, using two different screens to cover both preferences, and fitting the preferences of the one with more difficulties. Some users were pretty clear with the necessity of having a "wizard" that would guide the user to find the settings when a conflict like this happens.

3.2 Usability and accessibility of the SAT

3.2.1 Introduction

The main role of the SAT is to assist developers in integrating their solution to Cloud4all/GPII and mapping their settings to the EASTIN taxonomy and, consequently, to the *Unified Listing*. Usability testing sessions for this tool took place both in the 1st and 2nd evaluation phases.

3.2.2 Semantic alignment tool (SAT) (1st iteration)

The results of the evaluation of this SAT version were not good enough. Participants in testing found several issues related with the usability of the interface, the functionalities of the search engine and the ontology of parameters used. Several amendments were proposed in order to improve this tool in later versions.

3.2.3 Semantics alignment tool (SAT) (2nd iteration)

The developers' assessment of the Semantic Alignment Tool (SAT) was generally positive, though further improvements should be made both to simplify the technical jargon and to improve its visual design. Compared with the prototype tested in the 1st evaluation phase, the SAT was improved and developers considered it as a potentially useful tool to be used in the future (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Evolution of the ease of use of the SAT in different versions

3.3 Evaluation of the MM performance

Both the *Rule-based Matchmaker* (RBMM) and the *Statistical Matchmaker* (STMM) were evaluated in each of the three pilots. However, the evaluation procedure evolved during the project. These changes were due to the introduction of new features in the matchmakers and the GPII/Cloud4all infrastructure on the one hand, and experiences from the pilots on the other.

In each of the three pilots, the goal of the matchmaker evaluation was to determine how will the matchmakers scored in comparison with the “expert-provided solution”. The matchmakers were expected to meet the following success criteria in the three successive pilots:

- First iteration: All algorithms score at least 50% of the expert-provided solution.
- Second iteration: All algorithms score at least 65%, and one algorithm at least 75% of the expert-provided solution.
- Third iteration: All algorithms score at least 75%, and one algorithm at least 80% of the expert-provided solution.

The “expert-provided solution” changed in some important respects between the pilots:

- Whereas the first two pilots recruited end users with disabilities, the third pilot relied on experts in accessibility and assistive technologies (these experts were not necessarily persons with disabilities).
- In the first two pilots, users were asked to see whether they could work with the settings inferred by the matchmaker and then tweak them if necessary. The difference between the inferred settings and the tweaked settings was used to

determine matchmaker accuracy. In the third pilot, both the Cloud4all matchmakers and the experts (as “human matchmakers”) were given the same tasks, but independently from each other. As a consequence, the human matchmakers had to make their own choices instead of tweaking what the Cloud4all matchmakers had inferred.

- The first two pilots used (semi-)automatic mechanisms to log the inferred settings and the settings tweaked by the users, whereas the third pilot used a spreadsheet to collect these data for the “expert-provided solution”.
- The metric for comparing the matchmaker inferences with the expert-provided solution changed from a distance metric (in the first pilot) to a metric of accuracy (in the second and third pilots).

Below there is a summary of the matchmaker evaluation processes and their results from the three pilots. The goal is not to explain the evaluation processes in detail, but to provide sufficient information to understand how the data for benchmarking the matchmakers were generated.

In the **first pilot**, the evaluation process tested the auto-configuration functionality on *Microsoft Windows 7* and *GNU/Linux Fedora 18 with GNOME 3.6*. The first step consisted in defining a user’s needs and preferences. Since the PMT was not ready to be used for this task, the user’s settings were input in a temporary tool (the Needs & Preferences Gathering Tool or NPGT¹), which saved the settings to the Preferences Server. The user’s ID or token was saved to a USB stick. The second step was the actual auto-configuration on either Windows or Linux, and used either the Rule-based Matchmaker or the Statistical Matchmaker. The auto-configuration was triggered when the user inserted the USB stick into the computer: the matchmaker inferred settings for the platform (e.g. Windows settings inferred from the Linux settings gathered using the NPGT), and another component made sure that these settings were logged to a file. Finally, the user was given the opportunity to modify the settings in order to achieve an optimal set-up.

Then, the same process was repeated, but in the opposite direction; for example, if the user had gone from Windows to Linux, he now went back from Linux to Windows. The first half of the process gave us two sets of data: the Windows settings captured using the NPGT (A1) and the inferred settings on Linux (A2); the second half gave us Linux settings captured using the NPGT (B1) and the inferred settings on Windows (B2). (For other users, the order of the platforms was reversed, and this resulted in similar data-sets.)

¹ The tools’s source code is still available at <https://github.com/GPII/NPGatheringTool> but has not been updated since 2013 and is therefore no longer compatible with the current version of the GPII/Cloud4all real-time framework. Screenshots of the tool are available in section 3.3.1.4 of deliverable D402.2.1: Pilots evaluation framework, experimental plans and tools V1.

After the pilots, the inferred settings and the user's settings were compared using a distance metric, i.e. the data-set A1 was compared with data-set B2, and A2 with B1 (A1 and B1 represented the expert-provided solution). The distance metric took into account the specific data-type of value range of each setting (number, enumeration, string, etc.)².

In the **second pilot**, the evaluation process tested the auto-configuration functionality on Microsoft Windows 7 and GNU/Linux Fedora 20 with GNOME 3.10 and supported a wider range of solutions³. The first step consisted in defining a user's needs and preferences in one of the two following ways, depending on the matchmaker that would need to infer settings for the target platform. In the test process for the Rule-based Matchmaker, the user defined their settings in the Preferences Management Tool (PMT)⁴ on Windows 7, which resulted in a needs & preferences set (using "common terms") on the Preferences Server and an ID or token that could be saved on a USB stick or as an RFID token. These settings were also applied to the local system. In the test process for the Statistical Matchmaker, the user followed the same steps as for the RBMM and then also tweaked their settings directly in the solutions on Windows 7 (i.e. built-in Windows solutions such as the magnifier and the personalisation options in Windows' Control Panel, or installed solutions such as NVDA). The test facilitator then used the pilotsConfig tool to capture ("snapshot")⁵ these settings and automatically add them to the existing needs & preferences set (using "application-specific terms")⁶.

In a second step, the user moved to GNU/Linux (or a mobile device), where the user provided their token to trigger the auto-configuration based on settings inferred by one of the matchmakers. At this point, the test facilitator used the pilotsConfig tool to capture the matchmaker's inferred settings (log A1). The user was then given the opportunity to tweak the settings if necessary, after which the test facilitator created another log (log A2).

² The details for the metrics of each setting can be found on the wiki: https://wiki.gpii.net/w/Cloud4all_Testing:_Essential_Registry_Terms

³ The list of solutions can be found in section 1.2 (Technical preconditions) in Annex A of deliverable D402.2.2.

⁴ The PMT was developed in work package 102; its source code is available at <https://github.com/GPII/prefsEditors>.

⁵ The pilotsConfig tool and the "snapshotter" were specially developed for the second pilot. They were not used again in the third pilot. The code of the pilotsConfig tool resides at <https://github.com/Cloud4AllTUD/pilotsConfig>; the snapshotting code was part of the pilots2 branch of the GPII/Cloud4all real-time framework.

⁶ The definitions of "common terms" and "application-specific terms" as used in Cloud4all can be found at https://wiki.gpii.net/w/GLOSSARY_WORKSPACE#Types_of_Registry_Terms. At the time of the second pilot, the RBMM could infer settings only from common terms, and the STMM only from application-specific terms, hence the differences in the evaluation process.

After the pilots, the matchmaker inferences (log A1) and the tweaked settings (log A2, which represents the expert-provided solution) were compared to calculate the score of the matchmakers. In this pilot, the distance metric from the second pilot was replaced by a metric of accuracy because the distance metric did not convert well.

In the **third pilot**, the evaluation process tested the matchmaker inferences for Windows 7 and GNU/Linux Fedora. In addition to support for a number of new solutions, the third pilot also tested some important new matchmaker capabilities:

- the selection of a solution from several solutions that belong to the same category, e.g. deciding which screen reader to launch when two or more screen readers are available on the target system;
- the inference of alternative solutions and settings when the user's preferred solution is not available on the target system, i.e. identifying fallback mechanisms, e.g. increasing the screen resolution when the target system has no magnifier;
- the inference of settings on multiple layers without causing conflicts or other problems that can arise from triggering the same type of setting on more than one layer. For example, enabling zoom through a magnifier at the OS level and a larger font size on the browser level.

Instead of recruiting users, the matchmaker evaluation in the third pilot relied on accessibility experts that would serve as "human matchmakers". These human matchmakers were given the same inputs as the automated matchmakers (RBMM and STMM), supplemented with human-readable descriptions of these inputs. The inputs were JSON files with specific settings (expressed as common terms, not application-specific terms) and specific solutions or solution types required or preferred by the scenario's fictitious user. The inputs tested specific critical matchmaking scenarios that focused on the new matchmaker capabilities (see above)⁷. The accessibility experts did not get the matchmaker inferences as a starting point but made their choices independently, so the expert-provided solution was not influenced in any way by the matchmakers. The matchmaker inferences were generated at a different place and time, and these outputs were then compared with the expert-provided solution to calculate an accuracy metric. The metric used in the third pilot was the same as in the second pilot, but now also took the solution selection into account⁸.

⁷ These critical matchmaking scenarios are listed in section 8.2.1.2 of D402.2.3. The matchmaker inputs are available at <https://github.com/REMEXLabs/GPII-Matchmaker-Evaluation/tree/master/testdata>.

⁸ As in the previous pilots, the overall accuracy of a matchmaker uses the average of the accuracy for individual settings. However, in the third pilot, the average also takes the solution selection into account, so the average is based on the accuracy for the individual settings plus the accuracy of the solution selection. The details of this metric are available in deliverable ID403.3 (Results of Evaluation Phase III).

Another difference with the first two pilots is that we tested three statistical matchmakers instead of just one. The first one (STMM1) was based on all the training data that were available for the third pilot; the two other ones (STMM2 and STMM3) were based on different subsets of the training data. These additional “experimental” matchmakers were created to test the impact of different types of training data on the STMM’s accuracy. Further details are available in deliverable ID403.3 (Results of Evaluation Phase III) and in the STMM’s GitHub repository⁹.

Table 3 summarises the matchmaker accuracies compared to the expert-provided solution in the three pilots. For the explanation of the success criteria, see the beginning of this section. The results for the first pilot come from the distance metric, as explained above. The results of the first two pilots were also presented in deliverable D204.3 (Matchmaking Algorithms and Their Evaluation).

Table 3. Summary of matchmaker accuracies

Head	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3
RBMM	28% deviation	96%	81%
STMM 1	18% deviation	85%	53%
STMM 2	Not applicable	Not applicable	35%
STMM 3	Not applicable	Not applicable	36%
Success criterion	50%	65% (75%)	75% (80%)

Several observations need to be made about this table and the data on which it is based:

- The first thing that stands out is the decreased accuracy between the second and third pilots. As explained above, the third pilot evaluation was different and more challenging than the first two pilots. The new challenges related to the new matchmaker features, which require solution selection and/or the identification of alternative solutions. In addition, the human experts worked independently from matchmaker inferences, and this has an impact on the calculated accuracy of the matchmakers. In the first two pilots, when an inferred setting’s value was good enough for the user, that setting was not tweaked (or not very much) by the user, which would result in a high accuracy. In the third pilot, the experts did not start from

⁹ See the readme file in https://github.com/REMEXLabs/GPII-Matchmaker-Evaluation/tree/master/pilot3_stmm, which explains how to reproduce the three different STMMs and their outputs.

inferred settings but from a system (OS plus installed solutions) at its default, so they were never influence by a “good enough” matchmaker inference. The combination of the new features and the new test procedure apparently turned the third pilot into a harsher test. It is probably worthwhile to do some research into the difference between setting values that people with disabilities like best and the range of setting values that are acceptable.

- The sample sizes were small, and too small to draw statistically meaningful conclusions. This is due to technical problems in the first two pilots, due to which certain data were not captured or not usable. Instead of recruiting many users, the third pilot recruited a relatively small number of experts, each of whom was given several matchmaking tasks (usually three).
- In the first pilot, the setting that most frequently and most consistently caused a deviation from the expert-provided solution was speech rate (for NVDA and Orca), both for the Rule-Based Matchmaker and the Statistical Matchmaker. When the inferred speech rate deviated from the user’s solution, it was much more often slower than faster. Speech rate deviations in the second pilot were also slower than the expected rate. In the third pilot, speech rate values inferred by the RBMM were accurate from a mathematical point of view (i.e. using formulas that convert speech rate as a common terms into speech rate for a specific application) but could deviate from the expert-provided solution because the experts could only make rough estimates of how speech rate as a common term translated into the speech rate of a specific screen reader. The STMM sometimes generated speech rates that were outside the value range supported by the chosen solution, which resulted in low accuracy scores (and the identification of a bug in the STMM).
- In the first pilot, inferred magnification values sometimes deviated strongly from the users’ values. In the second pilot, the matchmakers achieved 90% accuracy for magnification (zoom factor), even though it was still the setting that deviated most frequently. In the third pilot, the RBMM reached 100% for zoom factor, but the STMM inferred magnification values of 160% for the Windows magnifier, although only the magnifier’s UI only accepts multiples of 25%.
- In the first pilot, some inferred settings never caused deviations, namely Orca’s enableEchoByCharacter and enableEchoByWord and its NVDA counterparts speakTypedCharacters and speakTypedWords, gtk-theme and icon-theme (for high contrast) on Linux GNOME and its Windows counterpart com.microsoft.windows.highContrast, text-scaling factor on Linux GNOME, screen-position (for the magnifier) on Linux GNOME and its Windows counterpart MagnificationMode.
In the second pilot, none of the settings were inferred with an average accuracy of less than 65% (the success criterion for the second pilot phase).

- In the third pilot, the STMMs responses for some of the inputs resulted in an accuracy of 0, which heavily contributed to the low overall score in the above table. STMM returned no settings at all for two of the inputs (4a and 4b in the GitHub repository mentioned above) that required the matchmaker to come up with a solution when no AT of the type required by the user is installed. In two test cases, STMM2 and STMM3 did not enable any of the solutions for which they were able to infer settings, which also resulted in an accuracy of 0.

The STMMs based on a subset of the training data performed significantly worse than the default STMM. This confirmed that having training data that represent just individual settings instead of full preference sets were a worthwhile addition in the last year of the project.

4 Cloud4all from the perspective of beneficiaries

4.1 User research with end-users

4.1.1 End-user involvement in Cloud4all

A total of 353 end-users have participated in evaluation activities in SP4. The user groups involved people with visual impairments (blind and low vision), hearing loss, deafblindness, cognitive impairments (intellectual disabilities and dyslexia), and elderly people. The full description of the user groups involved and the figures for each evaluation phase can be found in *D401.3. UCD and style-guide usage in the project* (Madrid et al., 2015). Moreover, the rationale and procedures for user involvement have been described in Madrid, Carmona and Montalvá (2015).

Figure 11. Two examples of user research activities at pilot sites

The previous chapter have described the results of the evaluation with end-users regarding the testing of Cloud4all tools, solutions and systems. In the next sections, we will describe additional research with end-users that have improved our knowledge on their needs and preferences regarding technology and the way in which Cloud4all could help them to overcome the accessibility barriers. User research with end-user have also provided ways of validating the Cloud4all concept, exploring those aspects that impact its usefulness and could determine the future use of these solution.

4.1.2 On users' needs and preferences with technology

4.1.2.1 Users' needs, preferences and conditional requirements

One of the main purposes of user research in Cloud4all was to understand the requirements and difficulties of a broad variety of individuals when using ICT products in their daily live. In a user study conducted with 97 users during the 1st pilot iteration, we explored the current difficulties and limitations users are facing when assistive technologies or customized accessibility settings are needed. Moreover we were investigating if users can actually specify their needs and preferences. The main findings are summarized here, but full details of the study can be found in Loitsch, Chalkia, Bekiaris, & Weber (2014).

In order to analyse the results of the user study, a differentiation on the requirements should be made based on the weight assigned to each accessibility settings. “**Needs**” refers to accessibility settings to be applied consistently across applications and devices or in specific contexts. “**Preferences**” refers to additional accessibility options that are preferred for specific conditions, but that doesn’t prevent the general usage of the product even if they affect their performance.

- **Needs:** TTS, Braille or combinations are named by blind people, while screen enlargement options (e.g. Zoom or magnification) are the most named feature between low vision users. Most of the elderly people claimed to have not specific needs but some of the also identified aspects related with font adjustments or simplified contents. Participants with low literacy, users with dyslexia and people with cognitive impairments identified less requirements as needs.
- **Preferences:** In this category participants claimed several settings that detail a basic need. For example, if one user set TTS as a need, it is probable that settings as voice adjustment, speech rate, punctuation, etc. appear as preferences.
- **Required accessibility settings for specific contexts:** Users would want to activate accessibility settings *always or conditionally*, and these condition could depend on content, application or device attributes. For example, TTS would want to be activated always or just under the conditions of 1) reading large texts, 2) when using text processing software but not with other applications, 3) TTS on mobile phones but not in PCs applications. The requirement could also depend on *the preferred AT product* (e.g. prefer to activate *ZoomText* over *Windows magnifier*). Finally, there could be also *dependencies between preferences* (e.g. do not activate magnification, if TTS is activated).

An additional result of the study was that there are, on the one hand, individuals who really know what they require to use information and computer technologies and, on the other hand, individuals that have no specific requirements. Based on the collected data, visually impaired participants, including low vision and blindness, have a basic understanding of the assistive technologies and accessibility settings they require to interact with their ICT products. But there are other types of users that are not so aware of the accessibility settings they could require.

4.1.2.2 User experience when configuring devices and applications

The need of configuration is a big barrier for users. They frequently find solutions that are too complicated, being difficult to set up and adjust manually. For example, specific difficulties are:

- Some people lack knowledge on their own N&Ps regarding technology, and therefore they can’t make adaptations even if they need it.

- Those users that are aware of their needs still found difficulties in configuring the devices they use, since setting up and installing devices and applications requires some technical knowledge and considerable time and effort.
- Some users need specific ATs that they have installed in their own personal devices, but are not present in (or are not compatible with) other private or public devices.
- Moreover, configuring devices and applications according to individual preferences is not always possible (e.g. administrator rights are needed in public devices or proprietary systems).

To overcome these barriers, the Cloud4all project provides new personalized ways of accessing devices and applications, by automatically configuring them in any place and in any context according to users' N&Ps. By doing this, it is expected that users will find easier to set up and adjust the systems to their specific N&Ps.

In the 2nd iteration, we further explored this issue. The users were invited to make configurations in the systems at different moments in the scenario:

- In Platform A (Windows), using the standard system controls
- In Platform A (Windows), using the PMT
- In Platform B (Linux, Android or Java phones), using the standard system controls
- In Platform B (Linux, Android or Java phones), keying-in Cloud4all

The objective was to explore users' difficulties in a realistic system, when they should make adaptations in new devices they found and want to use. The performance of the users in these tasks and their responses to dedicated user experience questionnaires were analysed and compared.

First, users were asked if they would like to make any configuration to the Windows system. Only 38 of 84 participants (45%) made changes in the configuration, while the rest 46 users (55%) didn't. From them, there were 22% of the users (most of them hard of hearing or elderly people) that claimed to have no need of any especial configuration. On the other hand, the main reason for not making changes was "not knowing how to make configurations", claimed by 25% of the users. Additional reasons for not changing configurations included the unavailability of the configurations required (2%) as well as others (such as "I need configurations for long tasks but not for this scenario" or "I will use the built-in browser zoom for this task") (6%). These results are summarized in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Configuration in Platform A (Windows) without Cloud4All

The performance of the users during configuration made clear a difference between those users with specific needs and those that only had preferences:

- Those users with clear interaction needs, such as blind users needing a screen reader or low vision users needing a magnifier, were really motivated to make changes in the system. However, the first challenge for configuration was to find and launch the screen reader or magnifier. For these users it is a prerequisite that the system should have the AT installed. Most of the users weren't able or didn't know how to configure the ATs by themselves. Only those experienced users tried to launch and configure the AT.
- Those users that only had preferences that are not essential for the interaction, as elderly that get slightly benefited from increases in font size, only made changes if they had high computer skills. For this group there was an initial surprise when discovering the Cloud4all concept and it may provide added value by making easier the configuration procedure.
- Finally, users that neither had needs nor clear preferences were able to perform the tasks with the standard configuration of the computer. For those users, it was not clear what would be the benefit of Cloud4all beyond the initial surprise of experiencing the auto-configuration.

Advancing in the auto-configuration scenario, the users were asked to use the PMT to set their needs and preferences. The results are summarized in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Configuration in Windows with Cloud4all (PMT)

In this case, the number of people that didn't make configurations because of the barriers decreased from 33% to 14%. Especially for the participants who did not apply changes because they didn't know how to do it, the percentage decreased from 25% to 7% of the sample.

Additional user experience metrics (*Perceived usability* and *Autonomy / Competence*) were measured during the configuration process to compare the usability and usefulness with and without the PMT. Results are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Comparison of *Perceived usability* and *Autonomy/Competence* feelings with and without using PMT

These results seem to point out that the PMT helped some users by making the configuration process easier, improving their autonomy and competence when making the adaptations in the system.

Finally, regarding configurations in non-familiar systems (*Linux*, *Android* or *Java* phones), some users tried to use the standard system controls before using Cloud4all. This seemed to be very difficult for all types of users because of their unfamiliarity with the OS. Especially, blind, deaf-blind and low vision users were not able to activate ATs or to change configurations (even when some advanced users tried to do so). Hard of hearing and elderly users were generally able to make configurations in *Android* and *Java* phones, although with some difficulties.

4.1.2.3 User experience when performing common tasks

One of the assumption of Cloud4all is that by providing N&P management tools and allowing for auto-configuration, users will be able to better and easier perform common tasks in different devices, being them familiar or not.

In the 2nd evaluation phase we tried to confirm this assumption by letting users perform common tasks both in non-personalized and Cloud4all personalized solutions, and comparing their performance and user experience. Common tasks were defined both for familiar solutions as *Windows* (such as reading texts or blog posts, writing comments or filling in a form) and for non-familiar solutions as *Linux* (such as finding, opening and reading & writing documents), *Java* phones (such as creating contacts or sending SMSs) or *Android* devices (such as managing contacts, changing ringtones or listening audio files).

The results showed that Cloud4all improves users' experience when performing a common task, both in familiar and non-familiar solutions.

First, in a familiar solution as *Windows* systems, it was found that the users were generally more successful performing common tasks, perceived them as easier and felt more autonomous and competent when the system was configured using the PMT. This indicates that by using the PMT to adjust the settings, the system is better tailored to user needs and preferences than when the user try to use the standard system controls (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Comparison of performance and user experience metrics in Windows with/without Cloud4all

Second, it was found that the performance and user experience with unfamiliar solutions was particularly poor without Cloud4all, but it significantly improved when auto-configuration was applied (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Comparison of performance and user experience metrics in Linux, Android and Java with/without Cloud4all

Notice that the general results with *Windows* are much better than those obtained with solutions that were mostly unfamiliar to the participants (*Linux, Android, and Java phones*). However, it should be taken into account that in the case of unfamiliar systems some users were not able even to access the solution before applying auto-configuration.

4.1.3 On end-users' concept acceptance

The participants in Cloud4all pilots assessed their acceptance of the Cloud4all concept in each of the evaluation phases. They based their responses both in the prototypes they tested and their expectations on how the system will perform when it will be finalised. Three main criteria were considered in the evaluation of end-users' acceptance of the Cloud4all concept: *perceived ease of use, usefulness and intention of use*.

Participants assessed the Cloud4all concept as **very easy to use** from the beginning of the project ('*Excellent*' in the UX scale). They were very excited with the simple procedures of collecting user needs, log in & out and auto-configuration of solutions (Figure 17).

Figure 17. End-users assessment of the Ease of use of the Cloud4all concept over the three project evaluation phases

Participants also consider it as **very useful**, in general, and especially for those users with low digital literacy or lack of technical knowledge, including the elderly. It may improve their autonomy to perform some actions, especially in public devices, where users do not feel comfortable with technology (for example, because they do not know how to use it or it is not configured accordingly, or they need to be fast because there are queues and people gets impatient, and thus they do not feel secure) (Figure 18).

Figure 18. End-users assessment of the Usefulness of the Cloud4all concept over the three project evaluation phases

Finally, participants also assessed their intention to use Cloud4all in the future as very high. The assessment of this aspect of Cloud4all have been positive from the beginning of the project, but it has significantly improved from the first evaluation phase, when the prototypes tested only allowed auto-configuration between *Windows* and *Linux* systems, to the second and third evaluation phases, when the prototypes tested allowed auto-configuration of a larger set of solutions (Figure 19).

Figure 19. End-users assessment of the Intention to use of the Cloud4all concept over the three project evaluation phases

Notice that, regarding the usefulness and intention to use Cloud4all in the future, end-users consistently claimed that it is much more relevant for public than for private devices. Most of the users thought that once they learn how to handle their own PC or mobile they will unlikely need to use a different one. It will be good if they could use PCs in computer labs at universities or libraries, or be able to apply their configuration automatically to a newly acquired smartphone. But the real problem that users experience in their real life is related with public devices as ATMs, ticket vending machines, information kiosks, and the like.

4.2 User research with developers

4.2.1 Developers' involvement in Cloud4all

A total of 77 developers have participated in the evaluation phases. Some of them are **internal developers** of the Cloud4all consortium who are working in the development of applications within the SP3 of the project. Therefore they know the Cloud4all/GPII framework since they have even integrated their applications with Cloud4all. Other persons are **external developers** outside the Cloud4all consortium who do not have any direct experience with the project or the GPII.

4.2.2 Insights about the integration process and Cloud4all acceptance

The focus of the evaluation with developers has changed from the first to the final round of evaluations trying to capture the developers' ideas on the evolution of the tools and the project potential.

In the **1st evaluation phase** developers had a first impression on what Cloud4all and GPII could offer for their work. They were optimistic about the Cloud4all concept, thinking that this will facilitate them to obtain global access to the AT and accessibility markets. Moreover, they agreed that the project would make easier to integrate accessibility features in the applications they develop. However, they did not feel comfortable with the SAT tool as described in the previous chapter and claimed for an improvement in its usability.

In the **2nd evaluation phase**, satisfaction questionnaires showed that developers were interested in the Cloud4all framework and were willing to integrate their applications in this framework. However, they still claimed for further improvement on the usability of the tools and the provision of documentation and training for developers. Several insightful ideas about Cloud4all were collected from developers at this stage:

- A general trend emerging from the discussions was that **additional resources should be allocated to dissemination, training and guidance on GPII, Cloud4all and accessibility in general.**
- Regarding the potential of the Cloud4all/GPII concept, **developers perceived the current AT ecosystem as rather complex and some barriers should be removed in order to maximize the adoption of the new perspective.**
- Developers also **recognized the added value of a market place for ATs and a recommendation system for users, but claimed for a more direct impact of accessibility in the AT markets.** Some suggestions were made, as matching the integration process with accessibility certification or other ways of making a product more visible that should be taken into account.

Finally, in the **3rd evaluation phase**, the focus was set on the experience of SP3 developers over the project duration. They were positive about the integration process, their comprehensibility, usability and usefulness, willing to integrate more solutions in the future

if they would have the chance to do it. They were especially enthusiastic agreeing that the Cloud4all/GPII framework would make it easier to create and distribute solutions that adapt to different users' needs and preferences. On the other hand, they were more moderated when assessing its benefits for moving solutions to the international markets. They think that Cloud4all could help to overcome the barriers imposed by the fragmented AT market, but there are other important policy and socioeconomic barriers that would not be completely removed with Cloud4all.

As a complement to this assessment, discussions in focus groups provided several insights for evolving Cloud4all/GPII in the future:

- **Installing GPII** was not an easy task from the beginning, especially in *Android* devices. This issue is also related to the documentation problems that are discussed below. The GPII installer will make these things much easier, at least in *Windows* systems.
- The **main benefits** of integrating solutions with Cloud4all from the developers' viewpoint are related to providing a way of accessing user needs and preferences stored in the cloud, allowing the solutions to be auto-configurable. This may allow an expansion of the audience for specific ATs that could access new solutions otherwise unreachable and unfamiliar to users.
- In the opinion of developers, there are still some **barriers for the integration of solutions with Cloud4all**. The main one is related with *maturity of the platform*: at this moment clearer documentation is needed regarding the steps to follow and much support from others to integrate the solutions. There are *other restrictions* that come from the proprietary systems or apps, such as the difficulties of changing app settings in *Android* systems.
- For the future, it is important for the system to be **reliable both for users** (i.e. a system that does not crash and are online on a 24/7 basis) **and for companies and developers** (i.e. stable specifications and APIs, including common terms).
- The **information required during integration** was not perceived as invasive or threatening for the confidentiality of the apps. However, sometimes it was not clear what information was exactly required for the description of a solution and it was hard to translate the meaning to the parameters. In addition, all developers claimed to feel comfortable with the open-source policy in Cloud4all.
- Developers thought that **much effort and human support have been required during the project** to integrate the solutions. This is partly due to poor documentation and the evolving nature of the project and, hopefully, better documentation and a stable system will reduce the costs and human support needed.

4.3 User research with stakeholders

4.3.1 Stakeholders' involvement in Cloud4all

During the whole project, a total of 45 stakeholders have been involved in the evaluation activities of the three iterations. Different profiles of stakeholders have participated along the evaluation activities in the three pilot countries:

- Social workers and carers of people with disabilities
- Representatives of organisations of people with disabilities
- Experts in specific disability profiles working at universities or governmental bodies
- Technology trainers and teachers
- AT product or service providers

Stakeholders were generally gathered in groups through the qualitative technique of “focus group”, obtaining very useful information from all of them. These discussions have allowed gathering their perspective about the general Cloud4all system and how it should work with users and developers in the real world. The participation of stakeholders in pilot evaluation has provided additional perspectives to validate the scenarios considered in the project, and to evolve the Cloud4all solutions in the future.

4.3.2 Cloud4all from the perspective of stakeholders

In Cloud4all, a dialogue took place with stakeholders on their proposals and priorities, their views and needs, including the results of this dialogue in the process of analysis and development. The evaluation with the different stakeholders was mainly explorative and not guided by specific research questions, but organized in different topics along the project. Those are the most interesting conclusions from the stakeholders' perspective that can be highlighted:

- **Cloud4all/GPII concept and auto-configuration scenario:** The potential of the Cloud4all/GPII is clear to allow people to use solutions for the first time, or to use them in a tailored way. The benefits of the auto-configuration capabilities could be even more positive and clearly appreciated in the context of public devices as ATMs or ticket machines than in private ones (e.g. personal computer or smartphone). The installation of GPII/Cloud4all in public libraries or other public institutions could also serve as good practice examples for private companies. The stakeholders value very positively the Cloud4all concept and outcomes, highlighting its ease of use and usefulness, as well as the easiness of the different login mechanisms.
- **The benefits for end-users:** The benefits are more evident for people needing adaptations or AT without which they are not able to interact with technology (e.g. blind people needing a screen readers to access a computer or smartphone). If Cloud4all wants to be also useful for people who have just preferences (e.g. increase font just to be more comfortable) or in the context of using private devices (e.g. use

the computer of a friend), additional effort should be paid to increase the appeal and the added value of the approach. The experts pointed out, beyond the functional and usable tools, the need of allocating resources for information, dissemination and training for end-users, their relatives and the professionals related with them, so they can harness the full potential of GPII.

- **Optimum N&P gathering scenario:** In general both solutions (PMT and PCP) were considered appropriate tools to gather settings, although some concerns were expressed on the level of expertise required for their use, thus possible solutions or ideas were recommended to introduce the tools to users as a wizard or a basic N&P set to avoid starting from scratch. The concept of the PMT and its functionalities had good acceptance from stakeholders, although they perceived it as more easy to use for experts than for the end-users, especially for those with less technological knowledge and the cognitively impaired. They recommended some improvements in the UI, as creating a simple version addressed to these profiles. However, although those stakeholders related to people with visual impairments were very enthusiastic, others related with different disabilities claimed to increase the number of supported settings in order to address the needs of specific user groups: 1) additional options useful for people with hearing impairments (e.g. subtitles, haptic feedback, sign language); 2) additional options for people with intellectual disabilities (e.g. enable easy language contents); 3) additional options for people with reduced mobility (e.g. voice recognition, mouse pointer speed, on-screen keyboard, etc.). Additionally, the Cloud4all solution should be flexible enough after being configured for the first time, being able to be modified on the fly and having a replacement solution if any failure occurs.
- **Context-related changes scenario:** Stakeholders found the context-related changes very useful, and completely agreed that context-related changes will facilitate the interaction with devices. A recommendation to develop these services in the future is to provide control for the user to decide under which conditions the context-related changes will be affected.
- **GPII marketplace and recommendation system scenario:** Both marketplace and recommendation systems are good ideas, but some concerns were expressed on how to implement them. Users should receive enough information to know and decide the best AT for themselves.
- **Cloud4all installer:** In general, the installer was well considered by stakeholders, although some hints for improvement were suggested. For example, since the range of abilities and technical knowledge of users is quite wide (e.g. people with intellectual disabilities or elderly users), this means that the installer as it is can be usable for some users but difficult to use for others.

5 Future research topics in Cloud4all

5.1 Research priorities from project partners

Based upon the great know-how the consortium gained throughout the project, they were asked to provide the evaluation team with ideas and topics that would need further research. Their proposals were also based also on the results of the pilots that have been sent to them during the project. Thus a template was sent to all the consortium partners as documented in ID403.4 (Chalkia, 2015).

As described below, the evaluation team made a compilation of these ideas that were categorized in two groups: *High priority research topics* (those that are very important to improve any aspect of Cloud4all in the future), and *Medium priority research topics* (those that are considered good to have but not crucial for the future of Cloud4all). This is not an extensive list of the topics needing further development in Cloud4all, but just an exploration of the future research interests for the consortium members.

5.1.1 High priority research topics

1. Multi-user support (also known as “dual preference process”)

- **Objective:** The objective is to provide solutions and settings when two or more users with different needs and preferences use the same device. This is especially challenging when users have conflicting needs, e.g. different contrast themes. See also JIRA ticket <https://issues.gpii.net/browse/GPII-805>.
- **Relevant field:** Matchmaking.
- **Rationale:** Sharing devices is a common scenario, for example family members watching the same program on TV, or children at school working together on the same computer.
- **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
- **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** 1-2 years after Cloud4all.
- **Author / Beneficiary:** TUD, HdM.

2. Context and activity detection affecting the use of the device and the needs of the UI

- **Objective:** Improve the information from the context of the user to adapt the UI properly to the activity or the situation that affects to the user. With the amount of information collected by GPII it is possible to detect activity or extend the context based on the relationship of the source of information.

- **Relevant field:** Auto-configuration.
 - **Rationale:** This research is based on the WP103 and related WPs.
 - **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
 - Developers of this solution.
 - **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** The time horizon depends on the level of definition of the context and the application of the information obtained by this point. The evolution of the information sources has a deep impact on this task so also influence on the research.
 - **Author / Beneficiary:** TECH, Eurecat.
- 3. An accessibility components database with smart interface for the users**
- **Objective:** User-friendly interface to search for AT Providers in the federated repositories DB and Unified listing. The interface should guide the non-expert users in finding the most appropriate AT for them (e.g. by asking simple questions).
 - **Relevant field:** Federated repositories DB, Unified listing.
 - **Rationale:** This research is based on the SP2 and related WPs.
 - **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
 - Training/Educational entities and personnel.
 - AT professionals (e.g. people working in assessment services).
 - **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** 2-3 years.
 - **Author / Beneficiary:** FDCGO.

5.1.2 Medium priority research topics

4. Connecting the SmartHouse emulation to a physical SmartHome environment

- **Objective:** To prove that auto-personalization and remote controlling of domestic appliances is feasible with devices.

- **Relevant field:** Smart homes.
 - **Rationale:** Applying the emulation concepts in real life is the natural next step for the evolution of the product.
 - **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
 - Home appliance manufacturers.
 - **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** N/A.
 - **Author / Beneficiary:** ASTEA.
5. Crowdsourcing “Try different”
- **Objective:** The objective is to provide solutions when the matchmakers don’t come up with solutions or settings that fit the user’s needs or preferences. When the matchmakers run out of alternative solutions, the matchmaking request can be forwarded to a crowdsourcing platform where it is presented as a human intelligence task. Humans then come up with a solution that can be proposed to the user at a later point in time.
 - **Relevant field:** Matchmaker Dispatcher, Architecture. Note: Crowdsourcing is not represented in Cloud4all.
 - **Rationale:** Even though Cloud4all has several matchmakers and these matchmakers can be requested to provide a different inference than their latest “proposal”, it is still possible that the user is not satisfied when the matchmakers have gone through all the alternative inferences they are capable of. In this case, the user needs human support. One way would be live contact with a support person who can provide a solution a real time. In the absence of live support, the matchmaking request (triggered by “Try Different” on the PCP) may be crowdsourced and presented to the user at a later time.
 - **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
 - Developers of this solution.
 - **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** 1-3 years after Cloud4all.
 - **Author / Beneficiary:** HdM.

6. Cross-platform mobile AT ecosystem

- **Objective:** Provide a Cross-platform mobile AT ecosystem for users in mobile devices.
- **Relevant field:** Mobile devices.
- **Rationale:** Good to have in Cloud4all, but it is something that is not possible with the current state of the art.
- **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
 - Developers of this solution.
 - Vendors.
 - Government/Policy Makers.
 - Training/Educational entities and personnel.
- **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** The time horizon is not very clear. The main restriction is that most of the mobile platforms are proprietary software.
- **Author / Beneficiary:** Emergya

7. Reducing the barrier to entry for integrators

- **Objective:** To find methods to reduce the workload and complexity of the integrating new application to GPII.
- **Relevant field:** Recruitment of participants and JSON files auto-generation from visual tools.
- **Rationale:** Enticing new third party entities to integrate their applications and devices will be a vital part of ensuring the success of the Cloud4all system “in the world”.
- **Audience:**
 - Developers of this solution.
 - Vendors.
- **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** A thorough research should be implemented on their field before launching it to the actual users, so the time horizon is vague at the moment.
- **Author / Beneficiary:** Omnitor

8. Support of auto-configuration of physical Braille devices by blind people.

- **Objective:** Allow a blind user to go to a technology, login using Cloud4all and be able to interact with it using his Braille device.
- **Relevant field:** Auto-configuration.
- **Rationale:** Blind users use to own very expensive Braille displays/keyboards that they use to interact with computers and smartphones that they own. It would be great to be able to use it in other contexts.
- **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (blind users).
- **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** N/A.
- **Author / Beneficiary:** Code Factory.

9. Testbed for sensors

- **Objective:** To have an increased level of trust for the values of the sensors. To be able to “calibrate” sensors remotely through an ontology of well-known devices.
- **Relevant field:** Sensors, architecture, matchmakers, algorithms.
- **Rationale:** When testing the environmental context we have detected plenty of different measures from sensors (different smartphone, motes, etc.) thus, it is difficult to have a fine grain of adaptations to user needs.
- **Audience:**
 - Users with disabilities (potentially all disabilities).
 - Developers of this solution.
 - Vendors.
- **Time horizon and restrictions / dependencies:** Can be done right now, though if new software deployments arise, it will be necessary to adjust the ontology accordingly.
- **Author / Beneficiary:** TECH.

5.2 Insights from user and expert forums

Three user forums took place in Linz & Berlin (July-August, 2012), Thesaloniki (December, 2013) and Madrid (September, 2015). An expert forum was also organized in Madrid together with the user forum in the context of the DRT4all conference.

Figure 20. Pictures from the user and expert forums organized over the project

Full minutes of these events are documented in ID502.1 (Peinado, Prentza, Melcher, Chalkia, & Madrid, 2015), but some insights for future research in Cloud4all are summarized below:

- **Improving the security and privacy of the storage and access to preferences.** Most users have difficulties understanding the procedures by which their needs and preferences are stored and accessed, where they are physically located and who could access them. These caused concerns that these preferences can be stored, get lost or be modified without permission. Together with improving the security and privacy of the system, additional efforts should be allocated to better communicate how these two aspects are addressed by Cloud4all. Experts have also suggested being in touch with dedicated organizations (e.g. *Electronic Frontier Foundation*) to be in line with current efforts and procedures.
- **Improving the N&P gathering process and increasing the list of settings supported.** Although some of the settings that can be selected in the PMT are very relevant, these doesn't cover the wide range of needs and preferences of users. Several users have claimed for additional settings related to speech input, sign language, text and interface simplification, etc. Moreover, not all users are equally able to define the best settings for them. Some have suggested that different mechanisms should be in place to allow for snapshotting the current settings and translate to other devices or to guide the user in identifying the best available options.

- **Further exploring personalization based on contextual and conditional settings.** Users claimed that, in their experience, the most appropriate settings cannot be decided in straightforward manners but depend on complex mechanisms. Apart from the fixed needs and preferences, there is a strong influence of the specific context (time, place, goals, solutions, etc.) in which the task is performed.
- **Increasing the number and type of solutions compatible with Cloud4all.** Users devoted much of their discussion to the potential benefits of Cloud4all to devices and applications that have been not included in the set of solution supported by this project. For example, they would like to see Cloud4all in public devices as ATMs or Ticket Vending Machines and in home appliances as washing machines and cooking assistants.
- **Developing a market strategy to make Cloud4all a mainstream technology.** Several participants in user forums have shown some skepticism that Cloud4all will success if the main players in the industry will not join Cloud4all. If Cloud4all just works as a pilot or in a residual set of solutions it will be very difficult that end-users will join this initiative. Participants in the expert forum also highlighted this issue, suggesting to approach and convince the main players and gather feedback from the AT industry.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable summarized the results of the evaluation conducted in Cloud4all over the three evaluation phases of the project. The aim of the evaluation was to enable the design iteration cycles: understanding the users' needs and preferences, designing and developing solutions, and conducting diverse types of evaluations of ideas, concepts, prototypes, in cooperation with all types of users.

First, we would like to summarize some **limitations** on the scope and results of this evaluation:

- The maturity of the different solutions was unequal at the time of testing, especially during the first and second iterations. This caused delays in research, but also prevented users in to have a holistic view of what Cloud4all could offer. In this sense the evaluation for the third iteration are more related to the whole Cloud4all concept while the evaluation conducted in the first and second evaluation are more influenced by the status of the specific solutions at the time of testing.
- Solutions integrated in Cloud4all were more relevant for some user groups than for others. For example, blind and low vision users were able to auto-configure settings for several devices, OSs and solutions that meet their specific needs and preferences, while users with hearing disabilities had more limited options. Therefore, although all types of users were able to experience the opportunities that Cloud4all could offer, some user groups had a more complete experience and hence they had stronger views.
- The liaison with external developers at later stages of the project was not as successful as expected. They perceived that the effort required to for the evaluation of Cloud4all was very high, and we didn't success in involving them in the assessment of developers' tools at this stage. Additional effort was devoted at the end of the project to provide developers with documentation, materials and tools (e.g. developers' kit) that could facilitate the future integration of solutions with Cloud4all and GPII.

The conclusions of this deliverable can be structured following the three operational objectives that guided the consolidation of results:

- **OO.8.11: To study all factors affecting the user experience with, and acceptance of the prototypes, including, perceived usefulness, ease of access and interaction, and satisfaction, and provide an integrated feedback for the enhancement of the posterior versions.**

Section 3.1 and 3.2 in this document provides an overview of the user experience evaluations conducted over the three evaluation phases. The end-users' assessment of the PMT/PCP prototypes has been quite positive, and the last version evaluated can be considered '*Excellent*' in terms of its ease of use. Moreover, the benchmarking

of UX metrics in the different prototypes versions has shown that the UCD approach adopted in the project have been effective for improving their usability, accessibility and user satisfaction. Each evaluation phase gathered useful feedback from beneficiaries about the PMT, PCP and SAT tools that were used by the design and development teams to create better versions of the prototypes.

- **OO.8.12: To provide iterative feedback for the development of each project prototype, with emphasis to the effect timing of the 3 types of matching algorithms.**

Section 3.3 summarizes the results of the benchmarks that compared matchmaker inferences with expert-provided solutions. The benchmarks helped identify issues in the support of specific settings and solutions and — especially in the third pilot — issues in the support of specific scenarios that require matchmakers to come up with alternative solutions and settings when the target system does not quite match the user's needs and preferences. The matchmakers appeared to reach their success criteria for the first two pilots, but the sample sizes on which the scores were based were statistically very small. The third pilot used a different approach to avoid recruiting many users; the combination of new matchmaker features and the new evaluation approach resulted in a good accuracy score for the Rule-based matchmaker (which fulfilled the 3rd pilot success criterion) but not for the Statistical Matchmaker (STMM). The issues that gave the STMM a low score will be investigated further.

- **OO.8.13: To review and consolidate the outcome and experience gained from all the evaluations and, thereby provide input to project development and exploitation teams as well as to the society, through guidelines and standardization recommendations.**

Evaluations in Cloud4all have not been only used for usability testing, but a wider user research framework was defined to gather insight on the Cloud4all concept and how it could better address the needs and preferences of the different type of project beneficiaries.

Regarding **end-users**, we explored the difficulties and limitations they face when ATs or customized accessibility settings are needed, their awareness of their needs and preferences and their competence to address them in a technology context. Moreover, we also analysed how Cloud4all could help these users to better configure and therefore to better perform common tasks different systems. Main findings are:

- There is a wide variability in the way users prioritize settings to be applied and there exist several conditionals for activating such settings or not. Therefore inferring the optimal configuration for a certain user is not a straightforward process and the full complexity of the context should be taken into account.
- Currently, users' found very difficult to configure a familiar or non-familiar system they encounter and want to adapt to their needs and preferences. Cloud4all tools

as the PMT benefit users by making the configuration process easier, improving their autonomy and competence when making the adaptations in the system. Moreover, it was also shown that Cloud4all auto-configuration allows users to better and easier perform common tasks, and make them feel more autonomous and competent in both familiar and non-familiar systems.

- When evaluating the Cloud4all concept as a whole, end-users scored it as 'Excellent' in terms of its ease of use, usefulness and intention to use it in the future. It should be noticed that they consider Cloud4all as more relevant for public than for private devices.

The evaluation with **developers** also addressed their acceptance of the Cloud4all concept and their experience during the integration process of their solutions. Although they were very positive in their considerations and the potential of Cloud4all, they also pointed out several issues that should be improved. They have found several barriers for the integration of their solutions, some of them are external to the project, but other are related with the documentation and the maturity of the architecture at the time the integration took place. These are difficulties that are inherent to a research project in which several components are developed and updated constantly, but seem to be easily addressed at later stages when a stable version of the architecture is in place.

Finally, evaluation with **stakeholders** has mostly confirmed the evaluation conducted with end-users. They have been also very positive in their considerations about the Cloud4all concept, but have stressed that the needs of some user groups are currently misrepresented in the N&P gathering scenario (e.g. no options for sign language) and that some users may need some additional guidance, especially those with cognitive impairments or low digital literacy.

To finalize these conclusions, it can be said that although the research with different types of users conducted in Cloud4all have provided much knowledge, it also generated new research questions that should be answered in the future. Chapter 5 in this deliverable summarizes some of these topics for further research. Some of them were identified by the consortium members that have proposed nine different research ideas that could be categorised into *High priority research topics* (such as *Multi-user support* to provide solutions and settings when two or more users with different needs and preferences use the same device) and *Medium priority research topics* (such as a *Cross platform mobile AT ecosystem* that it is good to have in Cloud4all and does not exist at the moment). Other research topics have arisen from end-users and experts participating in forums (such as *Improving the N&P gathering process and increasing the list of settings supported* or *Developing a market strategy to make Cloud4all a mainstream technology*).

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